

Welcome! We are a team of computer science researchers at ... investigating informal mentoring in open-source software community (OSS). Your input will help us identify the mentoring in everyday activities and understand how they impact projects. This survey contains 19 questions that should take approximately 8 minutes to complete. The results of this survey will be used in a scientific publication. By clicking the button below, you acknowledge that your participation in the study is voluntary, you are at least 18 years of age, and that you are aware that you may choose to terminate your participation in the study at any time and for any reason. Please contact ... if you have any questions or concerns.

EEA Data Privacy: Participants in the EEA are advised that data privacy laws have not been deemed adequate by the European Commission. For more information, participants can contact...

- I consent
- I do not consent

Q1.How do you identify yourself?

- Woman
 - Man
 - Prefer not to say
 - Prefer to self-describe (please answer as comment)
-

Q2.What is your age?

- 24 or younger
- 25 to 34
- 35 to 44
- 45 to 54
- 55 to 64
- over 65
- Prefer not to say

Q3.What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed? (If you are currently enrolled in school, please indicate the highest degree you have received.)

- Less than a high school diploma
- High school degree or equivalent (e.g. GED)
- Some college, no degree
- Associate degree (e.g. AA, AS)
- Bachelor's degree (e.g. BA, BS)
- Master's degree (e.g. MA, MS, MEd)
- Professional degree (e.g. MD, DDS, DVM)
- Doctorate (e.g. PhD, EdD)
- Prefer not to say

Q4.How long have you been programming?

- Never
- Less than 1 year
- 1 year or more but less than 2 years
- 2 years or more but less than 5 years

- 5 years or more but less than 10 years
- 10 years or more but less than 15 years
- 15 years or more but less than 20 years
- Over 20 years

Q5.How long have you participated (in any way) in Open Source Software (OSS)?

- Never
- Less than 1 year
- 1 year or more but less than 2 years
- 2 years or more but less than 5 years
- 5 years or more but less than 10 years
- 10 years or more but less than 15 years
- 15 years or more but less than 20 years
- Over 20 years (7)

Implicit mentoring can occur in everyday development activities like code reviews, where a mentor **implicitly** provides mentoring by giving an explanation when providing suggestions, instructions, or mechanisms to address errors. In contrast, explicit mentoring is where mentees seek out a mentor or are formally paired with mentors.

Given the definition above, please answer the following questions:

Q6. Please rate your agreement with the above definition of **implicit mentoring**:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q7. How long have you been in any implicit mentoring roles in OSS?

	Less than 1 year	1 year or more but less than 2 years	2 years or more but less than 5 years	5 years or more but less than 10 years	10 years or more but less than 15 years	15 years or more but less than 20 years	Over 20 years	Not Applicable (Never)
Implicit mentor	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Implicit mentee	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If How long have you been in any implicit mentoring roles in OSS?

Q8. Why did you choose to be an *implicit mentor*?

Q9. Please identify where you have engaged in implicit mentoring: (select all that apply)

- Email
- In person
- Pull-request comments on GitHub
- Comments on Stack Overflow
- Comments on issues list

Not Applicable (N/A)

Others, please specify: _____

Q10. Please rate your agreement with the following statements about the benefits of being an implicit **mentee** in OSS (1/2) :

Being an implicit mentee can help in...

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. Increasing my chances of promotion/higher salary	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Learning experiences beneficial to my job/organization	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Helping me grow my career	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Other benefits related to career growth (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
1. Improving my technical expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Improving my ability to transfer knowledge	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Improving the art of asking questions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. Improving my communication skills	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Improving my other non-technical skills (Including critical thinking, problem-solving, public speaking, professional writing, teamwork, digital literacy, leadership)	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Other benefits related to personal growth (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q11. Please rate your agreement with the following statements about the benefits of being an implicit *mentee* in OSS (2/2):

Being an implicit mentee can help in...

	Strongly agree (9)	Agree (10)	Neither agree nor disagree (22)	Disagree (24)	Strongly disagree (26)
1. Creating my collaboration network	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Identifying people who are domain experts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3. Identifying people who are programming experts	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Other benefits to social skills (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>				
1. Enjoying sharing experience	<input type="radio"/>				
2. Building friendship	<input type="radio"/>				
3. Other benefits related to altruism (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q12. Are there any other benefits you'd like us to know for being an implicit **mentee**?

- Yes, please specify: _____
- No

Q13. Please rate your overall satisfaction with being an implicit **mentee** in OSS?

- Extremely satisfied

- Satisfied
- Somewhat satisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Somewhat dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Extremely dissatisfied
- Not Applicable (N/A)

Q14.What were the reasons for your overall satisfaction rate?

Q15.Please rate your agreement with the following statement about the benefits of being an implicit *mentor* in OSS (1/2):

Being an implicit mentor can help in...

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. Increasing my chances of promotion/higher salary	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Improving my reputation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Improving my project's reputation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Other benefits related to career growth (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
1. Improving my technical expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Developing confidence in leading/managing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Improving my other non-technical skills (Including critical thinking, problem-solving, public speaking, professional writing, teamwork, digital literacy, leadership)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. Other benefits related to personal growth (please specify)

Q16. Please rate your agreement with the following statement about the benefits of being an implicit *mentor* in OSS (2/2):

Being an implicit mentor can help in...

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. Identifying potential collaborators	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Identifying other mentors	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Identifying potential contributors that can lead to career opportunities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Other benefits related to social skills (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
1. Receiving gratitude/appreciation from implicit mentees	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Improving my ability to impart knowledge and experience	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3. Enjoying observing the growth of implicit mentees	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Developing long-term friendship	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Other benefits related to altruism (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q17. Are there any other benefits you'd like us to know for being an implicit *mentor*?

- Yes, please specify: _____
- No

Q18. Please rate your overall satisfaction with being an implicit *mentor* in OSS?

- Extremely satisfied
- Satisfied
- Somewhat satisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Somewhat dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied

Extremely dissatisfied

Not Applicable (N/A)

Q19.What were the reasons for your overall satisfaction rate?

If you would like to be contacted for follow-ups to this study or know more about the outcome of this study, please provide your email address.
